

The logo for Cutting Gardens, featuring the text "Cutting Gardens" in white on a circular background with purple, blue, and teal segments. The background of the top half of the page is dark green with a pattern of colorful leaves and circles in shades of yellow, orange, blue, and purple.

Cutting
Gardens

Share knowledge
globally, build
competence locally

Returning in 2026

Introduction

Electroencephalography (EEG) and Magnetoencephalography (MEG) are powerful tools for investigating the living human brain. However, mastering the intricacies of a full analysis pipeline can be a daunting task. This is why the **CuttingEEG symposia** were established in 2014 to bring together scientists developing new methods for EEG/MEG data analysis with those applying these techniques to explore the human brain and its disorders.

CuttingEEG capitalised on the rise of online video conferencing to organise **LiveMEEG**, a large online event on MEG and EEG research practices. The event attracted a global audience, inspiring CuttingEEG to expand its reach to other communities worldwide. But traditional online conference models are limiting, prompting the organisation to collaborate with its community and to federate local events worldwide during its next event.

This is what **CuttingGardens** is about. It transcends the typical conference format by combining virtual and in-person engagement. The event unfolds simultaneously across various locations, offering a unified global program embedded in local sessions tailored to the needs of the local organisers, **therefore fostering global knowledge exchange while also empowering local communities to develop their own expertise.**

CuttingGardens brought together 21 independent local events across continents. Each Garden had its own unique blend of lectures, workshops, and satellite events. CuttingEEG provided a platform and resources to facilitate this global collaboration.

This report is an attempt to document what transpired at CuttingGardens 2023. Our goal is **to provide readers with a taste of the event's vibrant atmosphere and inspire future participants in the upcoming event**—stay tuned for what's coming!

Global Plenary Program

During 4 days,
12 speakers around the world
addressed 4 cutting edge topics
for analyzing MEEG data.

Theoretical Advances in Cognitive Neuroscience made through MEEG	Challenges and Opportunities in Real Time EEG processing and classification tools for Brain Computer Interfaces	Reproducible Processing Pipelines and Multiverse Analysis	Deep Neural Network Analysis of MEEG data
Introduction	Introduction	Introduction	Introduction
The Gut-Brain-Consciousness Axis Catherine Tallon-Baudry	Geometric Deep Learning meets BCI Reinmar Kobler	EEGManyPipelines Elena Cesnaite	Learning M/EEG Representations with Self-Supervision Hubert Banville
Tracking Attentional Dynamics Across Vision, Working Memory, and Action Freek Van Ede	Facing the Small Data Reality Michael Tangermann	The Data-Processing Multiverse of Event-Related Potentials Peter Clayson	Classic Machine Learning versus Deep Learning: Is there a Clear Winner? Maarten De Vos
<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>
Emergence of language during early development Clément François	Conducting BCI Protocols with Patients Theresa Vaughan	Agreed Reporting Template for EEG Methodology - International Standard Andela Šoškić	Using Artificial DNN to Predict and Understand Human Vision Radoslaw Martin Cichy
Discussion	Discussion	Discussion	Discussion

Simulcasted to
1000 participants
across **21 gardens**

The gardens

PLANNED ACTIVITIES

- Global lectures broadcasted
- Local lecture(s)
- Local tutorial(s)
- Local poster session(s)
- Local satellite event(s)

Belgrade, Serbia

University of Belgrade

Bournemouth, UK

Bournemouth University

Caen, France

Caen University

Donostia - San Sebastian, Spain

Basque Center on Cognition, Brain and Language

Dundee, Scotland, UK

University of Dundee

Frankfurt am Main, Germany

Ernst Strüngmann Institute for Neuroscience

Genova, Italy

University of Genova, Milano and Verona

Ghent, Belgium

Department of experimental psychology, Ghent university

Haifa, Israel

Developmental psychopathology lab at the University of Haifa

Havana, Cuba

Cuban Center for Neuroscience

London, UK

Wellcome Centre for Human Neuroimaging, UCL

Los Angeles, CA, USA

EEB, University of Southern California

Lyon, France

Lyon Neuroscience Research Center

Montréal, Canada

CRIUGM, University of Montreal

Münster, Germany

Institute for Biomagnetism and Biosignalanalysis

Nijmegen, Netherlands

Donders Institute and the Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics

Oro Verde, Argentina

National University of Entre Rios and IBB

Regensburg, Germany

Cognitive Neuroscience lab at the University of Regensburg

Santiago, Chile

Univ. de Talca, Univ. Del Desarrollo and Univ. Diego Portales

Talca, Chile

CINPSI Neurocog, Universidad Católica del Maule

Tehran, Iran

Convergent Technologies Research Center, University of Tehran

Gardens' local programs overview

129 Lectures
42% women

53 Tutorials

137 posters

Some outstanding local initiatives

'Get to know each other' session
social yet professional moments

Belgrade

5-days sustainable in research
Art-Science performance

Lyon

PostDoc lecture sessions to
promote early career researchers

Caën

Kindergarden to help researchers
with family duties

Frankfurt

Women leading neurosciences
round table

Oro Verde

An Innovative Event

Federal organization conducted collectively beyond borders

112 gardeners
52% women

CuttingGardens' model assets

- ✓ Foster international collaborative efforts
- ✓ Train a distributed network of instructors
- ✓ Shine a light on lesser-known but excellent research centers
- ✓ Join from anywhere: Allow access to people who can't travel to participate in the event
- ✓ Slash global conference costs by ~90%
- ✓ Ecological impact significantly reduced (see below).

CuttingGardens emitted <2% CO2 compared to the same event in one location

One location
1214 tons CO2

VS

CuttingGardens
21 tons CO2

Setting it up

Lots of gardening hours!

Two working retreats

Hacked BrainHack in BCBL Donosita

Team dedicated to the global production

